
Transformation Framework: Working Document

Mainstreaming Ecological Restoration of freshwater-related ecosystems in a
Landscape context: INnovation, upscaling and transformation (MERLIN)

SEPTEMBER 7, 2022

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1 Introduction

The EU Horizon 2020 project, Mainstreaming Ecological Restoration of freshwater-related ecosystems in a Landscape context: INnovation, upscaling and transformation ([MERLIN](#)) includes the aim to develop transformation strategies to mainstream Nature-based Solutions (NbS) to restore freshwater ecosystems. To achieve this the project is working with (public policy and market orientated) actors from different sectors, including Water Supply, Hydropower, Navigation, Peat Extraction, Agriculture and Insurance. This will enable MERLIN to contribute to achieving the EU Green Deal objectives (climate resilience, improved biodiversity, zero pollution, sustainable food systems, health and wellbeing). Although it is contended that transformation to mainstream NbS will emerge through multiple actions by the state, market and citizens, there is a lack of clarity about the meaning of transformation and how it occurs. In particular, the literature has framed the transformation process quite differently.

This (working) document aims to foster a common understanding of transformation and develop a comprehensive framework for understanding and guiding transformative change processes. The framework presented has emerged from reviewing and synthesising transformative framework from academic (e.g. Linnér & Wibeck, 2020; Löhr et al., 2022; Palomo et al., 2021) and policy (IPBES, 2019; SDSN, 2021) literature. The applicability of the proposed framework is illustrated using the peat extraction sector as an example. Further case studies of transformation in different contexts are cited to support the proposed framework.

We define transformation as a fundamental change in a social-ecological system involving qualitatively different patterns of connections, processes and feedback resulting in a different form, structure or meaning-making of a system (O’Brien 2012). Transformations can be purposefully navigated or unintended. Transformative changes are usually large and affect the dominant feedback loops (Moore et al., 2014) or the root cause of the problem (Chan et al., 2019).

The next section details the methods for developing the framework. Section 3 defines the key aspects of transformation, while Section 4 presents the overarching framework for transformative change. Section 5 tests the applicability of the framework based on peat extraction sector. Conclusion and next steps are provided in section 6.

2 Methodological process

Developing the transformation framework was an iterative process involving a three key steps. The first step was an appraisal process involving reflection on what transformation could be and the requirements for transformation. The appraisal helped to identify relevant academic literature related to transformation. Over 40 articles were obtained from online repositories and subsequently filtered based on the three questions in Table 1. For instance, the articles considered were those that provided a clear understanding of transformation in terms of elements and processes. Also, articles with transformation frameworks that could be operationalised or related to MERLIN’s objectives were further prioritised.

Table 1: Criteria for filtering articles about transformation

	Selection criteria – what does a framework need to encompass
What is involved in transformative processes	1. Identifies elements of transformation processes (not just categorising types of transformation)
	2. Involves different types of elements (e.g. practical/political/ personal; structural and agentic dimensions)
How to guide transformative processes	3. Links to how elements can enable transformative change (qualitative – not just quantitative understanding of an element)

	4. Engages with ideas of relationality as critical dimension of systems change (working through interconnections between elements, not single elements in isolation to guide change)
Operational	5. Can be feasibly used in MERLIN with <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. the available data b. research capacities in team c. Can link to a socio-ecological perspective (embedded in MERLIN and NBS)

12 peer reviewed publications were identified: each presented different frameworks for analysing and understanding processes of transformational change. In addition the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) global assessment report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services transformation framework (IPBES, 2019), and United Nations Sustainable Development Solutions Network’s (SDSN) adopted transformation framework to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Sachs et al., 2021) were also reviewed. Each framework was reviewed in depth against the criteria in Table 1 and through reflection on the pros and cons of each. The second step was the development of the framework. Here aspects of different frameworks (notably Fedele et al. (2019); Löhr et al. (2022); Palomo et al. (2021)) were brought together to construct a framework for transformation. The framework was developed from the perspective of WP4 in the MERLIN (i.e focusing on socio-institutional systems change of key economic sectors) with an explicit focus on mainstreaming NbS for supporting wider socio-ecological system transformation through NbS at the EU level. The final step was testing of this framework, using data from MERLIN activities (drawing on work undertaken to date in WP4 relating to the peat extraction and hydropower sectors).

3 Understanding and key aspects of transformation from theoretical perspective

The documents reviewed considered transformation as a fundamental and profound shift to a new system when the current system is untenable. For instance, Wolfram (2016) viewed transformation as creating a new system when the present system is unsustainable or cannot be operationalised. Many of these studies framed the **fundamental change** as a change that affects or alters the root causes or the dominant aspect of the system. According to IPBES (2019), the root causes include institutions, governance systems, culture and societal norms, technology and demography. Thus, although many frameworks reviewed were orientated towards sustainability and ecosystems social and institutional elements were considered key in shaping overall trajectory, including arising ecological outcomes. Sachs et al. (2019) also stressed that transformation requires “fundamental changes in norms, belief systems and cognitive heuristics”. The latter view is adopted in the recent Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Report (Sachs et al., 2021; SDSN, 2021), highlighting the specific areas where fundamental changes should occur to achieve transformation into the SDGs.

The meaning of transformation raises essential questions relating to (1) the system being transformed, (2) the purpose of the transformation and intended outcome (including whether the transformation occurs within the context of justice, equity and fairness), (3) the elements of the systems (what to work with), (4) dimensions of transformation (types of actions needed), (5) indicators to measure the transformation (how to understand if transformative change is underway), and (6) the phases or subprocesses involved in transformation (how actions interrelate to shape transformative change processes). These issues are explained briefly:

1. **System:** Transformation can occur within various systems. Studies have categorised the systems as either ecological (biophysical), social or socio-ecological. The **Ecological system** comprises the natural systems and related ecosystem systems (Moore et al., 2014). The **social system** relates to human-induced factors, including the norms, culture, governance systems, knowledge and processes (Fedele et al., 2019; Herrero-Jáuregui et al., 2018). The **socio-ecological system** refers to the relationship

between human (social) and ecological systems (Francis & Bekera, 2014; Herrero-Jáuregui et al., 2018). Transformation can occur either in an entire system or components of the system. Hence, the **specific system from which transformation is being considered should be clearly understood** (Palomo et al., 2021; Wolfram, 2016). The socio-ecological systems have gained ground because each of the social and ecological systems cannot be isolated, but they significantly influence each other. Hence, a **meaningful transformation should ensure a balance between the needs of humans and biophysical systems** (Palomo et al., 2021). Appendix 1 provides case studies of such systems.

2. **Purpose of the transformation and intended outcome:** This aspect recognises that deliberate transformation is a normative process, addressing the reason for seeking transformation (what is the new more desirable system). For example, to achieve the Paris Agreement or the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the IPBES (2019) recommend transformation in certain socio-institutional elements. In this case, the purpose of the transformation is realising the objectives and goals (i.e., sustainable, resilient future, etc.) as set out within the Paris Agreement or the SDGs. For achieving the SDGs six areas of transformation have been identified (Sachs et al., 2019). Along this notion, the purpose of transformation in MERLIN is to mainstream NbS to address societal challenges. This purpose will be elaborated in Section 4.
3. **Elements of the systems:** These are the specific aspects of the system that actors can work and alter to help effect the fundamental change at the system level. These elements interconnect in multiple ways – working within one element in isolation will likely be insufficient to bring about transformative change. The IPBES (2019) framed these elements as levers, focusing on governance elements such as incentives, capacity building, environmental law and implementation, and cross-sectoral cooperation. However, other studies show that the elements go beyond governance issues (Fedele et al., 2019; Löhr et al., 2022; Palomo et al., 2021). In Table 2, these elements could comprise political, personal and practical spheres. **Political elements** encapsulate governance, rules, distribution of power, procedures and economic issues, while **personal elements** relate to actors’ beliefs, norms and culture. The **practical elements** include the technical, technological and managerial aspects of the systems. A true transformation needs to encompass all spheres of elements.
4. **Dimensions of transformation:** The dimensions concern the types of actions that can be undertaken when working with elements of the system to guide transformative change towards a more desirable future system. Drawing from the work of Löhr et al. (2022), such actions could involve creating, maintaining or disrupting system elements. The transformation of wind power for renewable energy in Hamburg, Germany, exhibits these dimensions (see appendix 3 Löhr et al., 2022). **Creating** implies the need to bring into being new rules, spaces and practices, for example by promoting and defining targets and enabling experimentation and innovation. **Maintaining** requires adherence and replicating the existing good elements such as rules and beliefs. Maintaining does not mean remaining static: it requires taking actions that can amplify, strengthen or promote the widespread application of the elements. **Disrupting** concerns weakening, removing or interrupting the existing untenable foundations such as beliefs and assumptions and/ or may be hindering a change process. Achieving transformation is not just about building new institutions, each of the three groups of elements in a system could also be maintained or disrupted depending on their current conditions. According to Löhr et al. (2022), these dimensions imply that actions undertaken could build, reinforce or inhibit each other. Table 2 provides examples of creating, maintaining and disrupting the elements in a transformation process.

Table 2: Identifying the core elements (enablers) of transformation

Dimension	CORE ELEMENTS/ENABLERS OF TRANSFORMATION		
	<i>Political (Policies, institutional, economic and governance rules)</i>	<i>Personal and actors (Knowledge, values, norms, worldviews and beliefs)</i>	<i>Practical (technological, technical, management, and behavioural)</i>
Create new measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advocate and lobby • Narrative work, framing constructing identities • Define rules and set targets • Mimicking • Educating and learning • Create new mechanisms to promote engagement • Establishing new fiscal elements • Establish new power dynamics • Investing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrative work, framing constructing identities • Create networks, coalitions and organisation • Identify leaders and agents to promote changes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invent and experiment new landscape management practices • Implement for use • Narrative work, framing constructing identities • Mimicking • Educate and learning
Maintain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policing and enforcing • Validating the good practice and vilifying the negative ones • Preserving and emphasising the moral underpinnings of existing institutions • Strengthening and re-evaluating new structures to stabilize the weak rules • Sustaining and extending the rules and policies • Preserve power dynamics that can promote transformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserving and emphasising the moral underpinnings of existing actors • Strengthen new structures to stabilize the loose actions • Expanding and strengthening networks (this involves exchanging contacts) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validating the good practice and vilifying the negative ones • Preserving and emphasising the moral underpinnings of existing technologies • Upscaling innovations and diffusing them • Sustaining and extending existing technologies and innovations
Disrupt the untenable factors/elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oppose the existing practices and rules that resist change • Remove the existing incentives and supports • Restrict and sanction the existing technologies and practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oppose and disregarding beliefs and norms practices that resist change • Dissolve and replace the existing untenable networks and organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oppose and disregarding existing technologies and practices that resist change

Source: based on Löhr et al. (2022)

5. Indicators to measure transformation: Transformation is about a fundamental and radical change in the system. However, it is challenging to measure what constitutes a fundamental change (Palomo et al., 2021). Fedele et al. (2019) recently identified six indicators as characteristics of transformative adaptation. These indicators have also been adopted to measure transformation in nature-based solutions (Palomo et al., 2021). The indicators can help those involved in guiding transformation to characterise any shifts in social, ecological or socio-ecological systems (see Appendix 2) and thus can be important for evaluating progress and strengthening an adaptive approach that is essential when working within dynamic complex systems. These indicators are described from the social perspective since MERLIN focuses on the social and institutional transformation:

- **Restructuring:** Fundamentally reorganising rules, networks and processes (Fedele et al., 2019). An example is changing mindsets and practices, and increasing social and institutional capacity (Palomo et al., 2021)
- **Path-shifting:** Adopting an alternative development pathway. An example includes adopting different sources of income or financing.

- **Innovative:** Involves novel practices, behaviours and actions such as new technologies, eco-tourism and new forms of partnerships.
 - **Multiscale:** Transformation can occur at different levels or scales: state level, organization/institutional level/ local community level (Wolfram, 2016). This indicator implies a transformation that occurs across multiple scales and jurisdictions. These could include involving local and international actors.
 - **Systemwide:** It implies making the shifts widespread across societies and geographies. An example is implementing initiatives in multiple regions instead of a single site or going beyond the provincial scale to the national scale. Moreover, diverse and more stakeholders could benefit from an intervention instead of a few.
 - **Persistent:** It requires making future-oriented measures and can be established over several generations. Persistence implies adopting long-term instead of short-term measures.
- 6. The sub-phases/processes in transformation:** The decision to transform a system or create, maintain and disrupt system elements entails different subprocesses. Moore et al. (2014) identified four non-linear sub-processes. While these subprocesses are presented sequentially, Moore et al. (2014) contend that they may occur simultaneously. However, they are particularly important to help plan and guide in deliberate transformations.
- i. **Triggers or Pre-transformation:** Recognition that the system is becoming increasingly untenable (e.g. unsustainable) will often arise through major socio-ecological disruptions. It is important to understand the factors triggering or driving the transformation. The IPBES (2019) grouped these triggers as direct and indirect drivers. Direct drivers include land use changes, exploitation, climate change and pollution, while indirect drivers could be demographic, socio-cultural, economic, institutional or conflicts issues. Often triggers do not relate to an isolated disruption but involve multiple elements interconnecting to drive perturbations that may not be fully visible or widely understood yet.
 - ii. **Preparing for change:** Once the need for action is recognised (as in Table 1) to address the disruptions, developing an understanding of the system and its current trajectory is needed. This involves sensemaking to help interpret what is happening within the system, setting visions and gathering momentum (e.g. to coordinate resources) will be required. This may involve engaging with existing knowledge or seeking new understanding of the system.
 - iii. **Navigating the change process:** This is where actual innovative actions for the change is made. It involves choosing between alternatives, learning and working to enable widespread adoption of the measures.
 - iv. **Institutionalizing:** It involves routinisation, strengthening and stabilizing the transformation to embed new ways of thinking and acting within the system in ways that enable continuation of the new system trajectory through time.

4 A framework for transformation

None of the articles reviewed addressed all six significant questions of transformation simultaneously. Instead, the studies addressed different aspects of transformation. For instance, Fedele et al. (2019) focused on the indicators in different social, ecological and socio-ecological systems, while Palomo et al. (2021) examined the indicators and the system elements. Löhr et al. (2022) addressed the system elements and the dimensions involving maintaining, creating and disrupting. Moore (2017) focused on the subprocesses and the actions required. Other studies (such as Colloff et al., 2020; Pascual et al., 2022; Scoones et al., 2020; Wolfram, 2016) focused taxonomy of enablers, elements or governance of the transformation process.

The lack of a comprehensive framework is a fundamental gap considering that these studies acknowledge that systems being transformed are complex, making transformation non-linear and multidimensional (Löhr et al., 2022). Owing to this gap and the scale and complexity of MERLIN, the proposed framework must encapsulate multiple relevant aspects of transformation. Deliberate transformation involves defining the purpose and intended outcome of the transformation; understanding the nature of the system being transformed; working with and altering multiple elements or enablers; explicitly providing for reflection, evaluation and adaptive approaches, e.g. through process and outcome orientated indicators, and the dimensions of transformation. Also, it will be important to understand the subprocesses of transformation.

Figure 1 depicts a comprehensive transformation framework developed based on the questions in Section 3. The current untenable system is made of both socio-institutional and biophysical (interconnected) elements. These elements can be understood as relating to practical, political and personal spheres of systems. The dimensions of transformation represent that main strategic action area for guiding transformative change, involving, consideration of the need to create, maintain and disrupt elements that span the practical, political and personal spheres. Through the process of creating, maintaining or disrupting, another intended system could emerge. MERLIN should aim to meet as many indicators as possible to help embed and institutionalise the transformation within the new system. The purpose of the transformation – overall intended outcome – is ‘mainstreaming of NbS’ throughout Europe. Achieving this outcome will be informed by the IUCN global standards for NbS, characterised by the eight criteria. Thus, any transformation that does not lead to the mainstreaming of NbS may be considered unsuccessful.

Figure 1: A framework for transformation (Under development)

Source: Authors, 2022

The subprocess could involve the four main phases. For instance, in the first phases, there are triggers and drivers for transformation (Moore et al., 2014). To create, maintain or disrupt elements of the existing system, adequate preparation (2nd phase), including understanding of the system and establishing visions, is required. In MERLIN, the overall vision is to mainstream NbS as defined by the IUCN standards. However, developing a shared vision for what this would entail will be important, e.g. to help inform engagement with different system elements. For instance, when creating, maintaining or disrupting system elements, decisions may be informed by reflecting on the vision and intended outcomes, understandings of the current system and

transformation process indicators (restructuring, path-shifting, innovation, system-wide, multi-scale, persistent). The 3rd phase involves choosing between and acting on alternative solutions. Thus, a choice will be made on which elements need to be maintained (and strengthened), created or disrupted. The final phase is institutionalising the configurations. Specific actions are needed to stabilize and strengthen the new system that is emerging. As mentioned earlier, this is not a linear process. It is dynamic and iterative with many aspects of transformation being undertaken simultaneously. For example, some activities can be creative and disruptive. Ultimately there is a need to develop mutually-reinforcing feedback processes for meaningful, long lasting transformation to take place (Chan et al., 2019).

A major challenge to understanding transformation is the **counterfactual argument or identifying what is a significant or a fundamental change** (Palomo et al., 2021). While the priority for **MERLIN** is creating, maintaining and disrupting elements to enhance or expedite transformation to mainstream NbS, the entire process must be framed in line with global standards related to social **justice**. The IUCN Global Standards for NbS, which is the overall standards envisaged by the desired outcome is an important starting point. For instance, criterium six requires acknowledging and managing trade-offs through an equitable, transparent and inclusive process (IUCN, 2020). In terms of sustainable development goals, the IPBES (2019) framed the social justice requirement as a leverage point, including embracing diversity, reducing inequality and practicing social justice and inclusion. In this regard, we flag such standards as important considerations throughout the transformation process to ensure that the outcome becomes meaningful.

5 Testing the transformation framework for MERLIN

This section applies the transformation framework in two of the six economic sectors in MERLIN to demonstrate how the proposed transformation framework can be applied. This testing is important to improve understanding of transformation, including the elements and indicators. It is not exhaustive, drawing on work undertaken to date using WP4 data from desktop reviews, interviews, questionnaire surveys and roundtables discussion with selected sector stakeholders.

5.1 Description of the systems within the context of MERLIN

MERLIN's main focus is to mainstream and upscale NbS across 6 economic sectors at the EU level for freshwater ecosystem restoration. These sectors include the peat extraction sector and the hydropower sector. With a focus on the aims of WP4 (to mainstream NbS across these economic sectors), the type of system to be transformed is the 'socio-institutional context', which contains a range of interconnected elements. However, these socio-institutional elements are (directly and indirectly) linked with the ecological issues that we want NbS to address. As shown in Figures 2 & 3, each sector system can be envisaged as being influenced by external and internal factors that should be considered during the transformation process. The external factors include global conflict, global environmental standards, activities in the global market and climate change. Whilst it is beyond the scope of MERLIN, such factors can influence the transformation processes and what emerges. In the peat extraction sector, global market concerns include increasing cost of peat substrates, energy and alternatives to peat products. In the hydropower sector, such issues include increasing energy costs and mixed views about the sector's continuing relevance. Frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the Paris Agreement, and the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity are examples of international standards that influence both sectors.

Eleven internal elements could be identified across the three spheres in Section 3. Examples are provided for each element. As mentioned earlier, these attributes are not exhaustive, but an indication of some of the issues that need to be considered when deciding what to create, maintain or disrupt through the process. These elements and the external factors demonstrate why the present system is untenable and needs to be transformed. The specific elements in the peat extraction sector include **political** (e.g., existing EU regulations

on peat extraction, private funding of rewetting extracted peatlands), **practical** (e.g., fear of displacement, rewetting and rehabilitation as the main form of NbS, returning of land to landowners following rewetting) and **personal and actors** (e.g., policymaking institutions, umbrella organisations such as the IPS and belief that peat extraction imposes minimal environmental impact on peatlands compared with functions such as agriculture).

Figure 2: Components of the peat extraction system

Figure 3: Components of the hydropower sector and dams' system

The current system elements and features offer both opportunities and challenges. For instance, the power relations, limited knowledge about NbS, and the already dominant systems of peat extraction are challenges, while the existing laws and institutions can be opportunities. The challenges and opportunities are elaborated in the literature review and the briefings. The idea is that the next step is to identify those attributes that should be **created, maintained** and **disrupted** to effect transformation into NbS systems in the sector. Understanding the current system features corresponds with the first and second phases of transformation (understanding triggers and preparing for change). The EU Green Deal objectives (opportunity) and the climate change and CO₂ emissions (challenges) are among the major triggers for transformation.

5.2 Changes required in the peat extraction sector

Based on the current condition of the peat extraction sector, a proposal could be developed for transformation. Table 3 presents the specific changes (based on available data) that could be made through creating, maintaining and disrupting elements within the sector. In terms of **political elements**, 'creating' interventions could occur by developing a specific policy framework for the extraction of peat and the implementation of NbS in the peat extraction sector. This policy is needed given that the peat extraction sector does not have a specific EU-wide policy but relies on thematic or other sectoral policies such as the Water Framework Directive, Common Agriculture Policy and Soil Thematic Strategy. Some of these policies conflict with the restoration needs of the sector. In some cases, member states rely on separate policies, which implies different regulatory processes are followed. The new policy could address these gaps. It could also influence other subsequent elements that need to be created, maintained and disrupted for mainstreaming NbS.

For instance, the policy could establish incentive mechanisms to subsidise the cost of implementing NbS on extracted peatlands. Presently, the rewetting that is being undertaken by the sector does not meet the IUCN standards for NbS because standards such as design at scale, inclusivity and mainstreaming for sustainability are not exhibited. The new policy could require peat extraction companies to incorporate a comprehensive NbS proposal during licensing process. Concurrently, there could be incentives for such companies to design NbS at scale instead of site level rewetting.

'Maintaining' within the **political elements** could include harmonising and strengthening the current policies, links with other existing policies relevant to peat extraction and ensuring the policy conflicts are addressed. The tasks align with the analogy that existing policies are good opportunities but need to be integrated into the mainstream peat-extraction practices and NbS implementation. The current private funding responsibilities could be expanded beyond the site level. However, attention may also be required towards developing the capacity of key actors to access these (i.e. also working in the personal sphere). For instance, during licensing process, an extra percentage of land outside the peat extraction site could be added to the restoration responsibilities of peat extraction companies.

A 'disrupting' intervention could involve scraping the previous existing licenses permitting peat extraction on pristine peatlands. Although presently new peat extraction licenses are not permitted on pristine peatlands, licenses granted years ago on such peatlands are still operating. This phenomenon implies that some original peatlands are being interrupted. To strengthen the drive for transformation and protection of wetlands, scraping such existing licenses will ensure that such pristine lands are not disturbed further. In addition, the timeline for extracting peatlands could be reduced to ensure that the peat is not completely exploited beyond their capacity to regenerate.

Creating, maintaining and disrupting actions could be undertaken in the practical, personal and actor elements. In the **personal and actors' sphere**, 'creating' interventions could involve sensitization of the extraction companies that the peat extraction, irrespective of their land coverage or proportions of carbon emissions, has impacts that cannot be ignored. This creating action could simultaneously also contribute to disrupting elements that may be hindering change within the sector, for example in terms of opposing the

current belief within the sector that current activities impose minimal environmental impacts compared with other sectors. Creating action in the practical element could also include experimenting with new NbS measures and insisting on the NbS instead of just rewetting on extracted peatlands. The maintaining intervention could involve expanding the existing rewetting practices on a landscape basis instead of site level.

Table 3: Proposed changes for transformation in the peat extraction sector (R = Restructuring, PS = Path-Shifting, I = Innovative, M = Multiscale, S = Systemwide, P = Persistent)

Dimension	CORE ELEMENTS/ENABLERS OF TRANSFORMATION		
	<i>Political (Policies, institutional, economic and governance rules)</i>	<i>Personal and actors (Knowledge, values, norms, worldviews and beliefs)</i>	<i>Practical (technological, technical, management, and behavioural)</i>
Create new measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop policy specifically for peat extraction and NbS implementation on peatlands (R, S, P) Public sector acquisition of extracted peatlands (PS) Establishing new incentive for landowners to use extracted peatlands for NbS (I, R, PS) Educating landowners (R) New incentives and subsidies for peatlands to peat restored earlier than duration approved in extraction license (I, R, PS) Public sector support for landscape peatland restoration (R) Requiring peat extraction companies to incorporation a comprehensive NbS proposal during licensing process (R, PS). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensitise peat extraction companies that extraction poses some risk to peatlands (R) Create new communities of practices specifically for owners of peatlands (I, PS, M) New network between peat extraction industries and landowners (R, I, M) Building the confidence and assuring the peat companies that they stand to gain from increased NbS implementation (R, P) New platform for dialogue and cooperation between public actors and peat extraction companies (R, I, M, S) Improving collaboration between peat extraction sector and related sectors (R) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insisting on NbS implementation instead of alternative use of land or create multi-functional use of extracted peatlands with NbS as the focus (R, P) Establish case studies to experiment NbS on extracted peatlands on landscape basis (I) Experiment multifunctional and economic use of extracted peatlands using NbS (I, PS) Integrating other forms of NbS such as revegetating and afforestation with rewetting (R, PS) Developing guidelines for NbS implementing in the sector (R, I) Inter-state platform to share experiences and learn from best practices (M, S)
Maintain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Harmonising the current sector policies linked with peat extraction (R) Bringing into play the international frameworks (e.g. Paris Agreement) (R, M) Strengthening and harmonising the licensing process across EU States (R, M) Equipping the existing institutions to understand peat extraction and restoration of extracted peatlands (R) Stabilizing and widening private funding responsibilities about restoration of extraction peatlands (e.g. to include a % of lands outside extracted jurisdiction) (R, I, PS) Expanding the voluntary climate compensation schemes and payment for ecosystem services (R, S) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen and expand the existing communities of practice to include new actors (M, S) Expanding the role of umbrella organisations (R, M, S) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expand the current rewetting practices to meet NbS standards (e.g. Encouraging NbS beyond site-level) (R, S) Making it easier to access sphagnum moss layer transfer ensuring there is minimal negative impacts on existing peatlands (R)

Disrupt the untenable factors/elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scraping the previous existing licenses permitting peat extraction on pristine peatlands (R, PS, P) • Removing the bureaucratic requirement of restoring peatlands earlier than the duration granted by licences (R) • Reducing the duration taken to extract peat on a single peatland (R) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oppose the idea that peat extraction poses minimal risk to peatlands compared with other activities (R) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insisting that rewetting alone is not enough (I, PS)
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In each of the suggested changes, the second and third phases of the transformation process would be considered. For the **second phase**, a clear shared vision needs to be co-developed, informed by credible knowledge to understand the current condition of the system. For example, research could focus on an inventory of actual emissions resulting from the peat extraction, the total number of peat extraction companies, total land coverage used for peat extraction and the economic contribution from the sector. This phase is important to inform the choices made about what actions are needed to navigate the change process (the third phase). Such decisions may involve choosing which proposed actions in Table 3 to pursue in practice. For instance, there is a choice to be made, whether to create a new policy instrument or to consolidate and strengthen the existing policies. There is also a choice to be made on whether scrap the previous permits for peat extraction on pristine peatlands or to main the licenses. Each choice requires experimentation and deliberations (e.g. in terms of individually and cumulative achieving the desired outcomes) before their widespread uptake. These decisions and activities must be equitable and inclusive with a foresight of meeting the IUCN standards. This can therefore also be considered an ongoing process of reflection, learning and action.

5.3 Indicators for the changes

As mentioned earlier, the indicators help to measure the extent to which transformation is occurring. While a single activity and the change that emerges could exhibit multiple indicators, such change may relate more to a particular indicator than others (see Table 3). For instance, developing a new policy framework for the peat extraction sector (i.e., creating political intervention) could contribute to indicators:

- *Restructuring* in terms of reorganising the existing policy framework related peat extraction into a single policy.
- *Systemwide* in terms of ensuring that the policy is applied throughout the EU and benefits are distributed widely.
- *Persistent* by ensuring that the new policy is embedded within other policies to have a long-term duration.

Moreover, establishing new incentives for landowners to use extracted peatlands for NbS can be evaluated in terms of innovation, restructuring and path-shifting criteria because such incentives could be freshly created, or an alternative existing incentive mechanism could be adapted and adopted instead of the existing one.

In the personal element, creating new communities of practices *could* contribute to innovation, path-shifting, systemwide and multiscale indicators. In terms of innovation and path-shifting the communities could depart from the current engagement practices where the communities only comprise sector experts and academics. The landowners could also be incorporate into the communities to increase understanding of NbS on peatlands. The multiscale indicator ensures that the new communities cover the EU, national and local levels. Systemwide indicator could ensure that the new communities are widespread and inclusive across sectors and stakeholder groups, instead of just within a particular subset. Finally, practical interventions such as collaborative platforms to learn from best practices are to enhance multi-scale and systemwide indicators.

Thus, the platform could ensure that NbS covers multiple countries in Europe, and simultaneously help in scaling out good practices at the national level.

6 Conclusion and next steps

This document proposed a transformation framework for MERLIN to inform decisions about what is needed to help achieve its objectives. The ideas in the document are not definitive and are still evolving (and we welcome your feedback). The aim is to evoke further discussion and understanding about the perspectives from which transformation could be considered. An important message, however, is that transformation within complex systems requires radical actions, reflection and learning. Focusing on the European context involves considering different layers of actors, challenges, sectors and governance frameworks. Some of these layers may have conflicting interests and motivations. Hence, there is the potential to make friends and build new alliances and sometimes ‘enemies’, who may hinder or actively resist aspects of the process. Therefore, the change process should be navigated cautiously with justice, equity and fairness. The framework in this document has been simplified in a power-point presentation. Next steps include discussing the concepts, receiving feedback and considering how the framework could be applied to the MERLIN sectors and case studies.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Examples to highlight transformations.

NOTE: Not sustainability transformations (very contested/ subjective if sustainability of system has ‘succeeded’ – definitive improvement in some cases (with exception of 1 and 2 – which arguably lead to poorer env and soci sust dimensions)).

	Possible system transformation examples	Nature of Transformation	Time frame	Key triggers	Elements that changed (international and unintentional)
1	The Asteroussia Mountains (Crete) land management system (Kizos et al., 2014)	From: Semiarid husbandry To: Subsidized husbandry	1980's - 2008	Agricultural subsidies in the 1980s and onward External inputs and cash availability	Land management practices – including abandonment of long-term care for the land and more intensive grazing. Social relationships, trust and capacity for collective action. NB no NbS – led to loss of social capital and natural capital – hindering resilience.
2	Subtropical dairy industry in Australia (Sinclair et al., 2014)	From: Government controlled To: Market driven	2000 - 2011	National Competition Policy (NCP), a package of microeconomic reforms that triggered market deregulation	Higher loss of farms Weakened farmer networks, cooperation, poorer animal welfare Increases in competition, debt, mean farm area, herd size, and cow production Lower levels of investment in farm businesses Concentration of power by supermarkets (with generic branding) Greater reliance on business consultants NB no NbS – led to loss of social capital and resilience
3	Energy system in City of Graz, Austria https://cites.eerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.879.2003&rep=rep1&type=pdf	From: City To: ‘Eco-city’	1990's - present	Environmental deterioration (e.g. smog winter of 1988/89) group of engaged citizens became active in the field of urban environmental and energy policy	long-term institutional changes and programmes which still contribute to energy system change to demand side energy management International attention and awards Unclear if NbS involved – I think not.

				<p>pressurizing for change</p> <p>entrepreneurial spirit of a few key persons in local government administration</p>	
4	<p>Rieselfeld and Vauban neighbourhoods, City of Freiburg, Germany</p> <p>(Mahzouni, 2018; Miller & Mössner, 2020)</p> <p>https://cites.eerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.879.2003&rep=rep1&type=pdf</p> <p>https://www.witpress.com/Secure/ejournals/papers/D%26NE080401f.pdf</p> <p>https://greencity.freiburg.de/pb/Len/milestones.html</p>	<p>From: Brownfield land</p> <p>To: sustainable neighbourhoods/ green city (multiple scale)</p>	1990's - present	<p>a broad range of environmentally engaged civil society initiatives have been able to build up and keep up momentum</p>	<p>local utilities (gas, electricity, water), merged with other municipally owned utilities of the region</p> <p>Focus on efficient power and heat generation, building efficiency (policies, standards, infrastructure)</p> <p>Development energy efficient, low traffic neighbourhoods with green space and conservation area (amongst other initiatives) from brownfield land</p>
5	<p>South Korea - Forest ecosystem management</p> <p>https://4fqbk2blqkb1nrebde8yxqj-wpengine.netdna-ssl.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/18.-Forest-transition-in-South-Korea-A-miracle-made.pdf</p>	<p>From: exploitation</p> <p>To: Ecosystem-based disaster risk reduction</p>	1970's - present	<p>Annual flooding and landslides</p> <p>Presidential visit to Germany</p> <p>'First National Forest Plan' of 1973</p>	<p>encouraged citizens and village cooperatives to participate not in a tree-planting programme but in a 'movement', successfully invoking national service with slogans like 'Planting is loving the Nation'</p> <p>First goal of planting 2.8 billion trees over one million hectares of denuded forest was achieved in 1979 — four years ahead of schedule.</p> <p>The Second Plan from 1979-1989 upped the sophistication levels, deploying research and soil surveys to choose site-specific species to plant, and placing more emphasis on commercial-scale production forests with more diverse species mixes (but still with more non-native than native species).</p> <p>Long term vision, consistent funding, public outreach and effective</p> <p>forest stocks eventually increase from just under 10m3 per hectare to 146m3 per hectare by 2010 – with stocked forest area (or density of trees) massive increasing, total forest area declined - showed the world that increasing tree cover and growing carbon stocks on existing degraded forest land can be done.</p> <p>South Korean forest covers about 64% of the territory and generates about \$US103 billion dollars worth of ecosystem services</p>
6	<p>Transbay Transit Center (urban</p>	<p>From: Bus transit terminal</p>	1990's/ 2000's - 2018	<p>1989 Loma Prieta earthquake</p>	<p>Roof developed as a 5.4 are roof top park – a living roof providing extensive green space, open and accessible to all (although locked at in the evenings), with interactive water features, with space for contemplation /relaxing and to bring people together.</p>

	<p>infrastructure)—San Francisco https://salesforcetransitcenter.com/about/ https://cdn.vox-cdn.com/uploads/chorus_asset/file/11966757/TransbayTransitCenter_PCharging_0044.jpg https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Transbay_Transit_Center</p>	<p>To: A multifunctional, intermodal transport hub</p>			<p>Transit centre for improved connectivity (bus and tram network and future rail and tube services), utilising natural light, art installations and nature inspired design.</p>
7	<p>New Zealand – hydropower governance (Chapin III et al., 2012)</p>	<p>From: pathway of environmental deterioration To ecosystem stewardship approach (freshwater)</p>	<p>1970-present</p>	<p>Major public outrage over the ecological and aesthetic implications of raising lake levels to maximize (hydropower) power output with a petition that was signed by about 10% of the nation’s adult population demanding renegotiation of hydropower contract with smelter change in central government in 1972 The concept of sustainable management of natural resources, inherent in this controversy informed the Resource Management Act in 1991</p>	<p>Established lake Guardian Groups who renegotiated (with skilled facilitation) the resource management of the water-related ecosystem services associated with a hydroelectric development. The final agreements included; maintaining lake levels within their natural historic limits, a guaranteed minimum flow of the (lower) River draining the Lake to restore habitat for fish and other aquatic biota, funding for the restoration of wetlands that had been modified by the associated river management, compensation to local Māori people for loss of traditional food resources, optimizing power production within these constraints. The Guardians of the Lakes now have three lakes under their jurisdiction, are now enshrined in law, and they continue to monitor and advise on water management to ensure an acceptable balance between ecological sustainability and power delivery NB guardian groups also established to manage marine fisheries – with triggers being declining stocks and concerns about future sustainability – supported by government funding</p>

				Strong cultural dimensions/ sense of place	
8	<p>Antoing area (Belgium) Local water management regime</p> <p>https://www.wbcscd.org/Programs/Food-and-Nature/Water/Resources/Case-studies/From-discharge-to-supply-water-reuse-at-Antoing-quarry</p> <p>http://docs.wbcscd.org/2017/09/Water/CircularWaterManagementCaseStudyHC.pdf</p>	<p>From: Unsustainability water management</p> <p>To: water sharing and reuse</p>		<p>Increasing scarcity of water involving over exploitation of aquifer</p>	<p>Instead of discharging 'wate' water this was diverted to public water company – enabling them to reduce reliance of groundwater abstraction. = Supply and value chain approach</p> <p>NB/ No NbS</p>
9	<p>Manilla water company, Philippines</p> <p>https://iwa-network.org/climate-smart-utilities-philippines/</p>	<p>From: Water supply</p> <p>To: catchment scale climate smart water management</p>	2007-present	<p>Changing climate</p> <p>Company climate change policy</p>	<p>Conscious organisational cultural shift to implementation of climate change mitigation and adaptation initiatives throughout the entire business for water quality and quantity</p> <p>Wide-spread use of nature-based solutions ("<i>Nature-based solutions (NbS) have also been incorporated into Manila's water adaptation actions. The utility funds projects to implement watershed protection and management of activities in relevant watersheds, such as the Ipo, La Mesa, Upper Marikina, General Nakar, Nabaoy, Pan-as Hayiban and Villa Maria. As of 2021, the company rehabilitated a total of 2459 hectares with 1,255,612 native trees planted and nurtured in these watersheds since 2006. Protecting these watersheds not only safeguards them from further environmental degradation, but also contributes to their sustainable role in mitigating climate change</i>")</p> <p>Environmental education programme</p>
10	<p>Water governance, The Netherlands</p> <p>(Global Centre on Adaptation, 2021; van Popering-Verkerk & van Buuren, 2017)</p> <p>https://www.dutchwatersector.com/news/room-for-the-river-programme</p>	<p>From prevention/ command and control</p> <p>To: Living with water and working with nature</p>	2000's - present	<p>Widespread flooding in delta regions in 1993 and 1995</p> <p>2006 spatial planning key decision</p>	<p>growing understanding it was impossible to predict and control nature,</p> <p>The past could not reliably inform the future</p> <p>Safety remains a priority a systems approach is being adopted (i.e. principles of multifunctionality).</p> <p>Nature based solutions - Room for River programme 2007-2022 and</p>

11	Urban planning in Curitiba, Brazil (Rosário, 2016)	From: City under pressure from rapid population growth To: Thriving historic centre and one of the greenest cities in Brazil	1970s - present	New vision ('A setting for encounters) for the city and establishment of a local planning office by team of young, creative local professionals	an extensive integrated public transit network land-use policies that channels development along linear corridors; The Transfêrencia de Potencial Construtivo initiated in the early 1980s that allows owners of historic buildings to sell their building rights elsewhere as long as they restore and maintain the property. Adaptive governance approach – e.g. Delta programme
12	The Great Barrier Reef Marine Park (Olsson et al., 2010) https://www2.gbrmpa.gov.au/	Transforming ecosystems and addressing degradation due to runoff, oil spillage, overharvesting, population growth	1970s – early 2000s	Human pressure and climate change	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enacting The Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Act in 1975; 2. Establishing a new agency, Marine Park Authority 3. Major rezoning of the marine park (Representative Areas Program (RAP)) 4. Adopting a holistic management approach 5. Skilful leadership 6. The Senior Managers Forum <p>According to Olsson et al. (2010), five important areas addressed are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internal organizational changes 2. bridging science and policy 3. changing people's perceptions 4. facilitating public consultation and participation 5. gaining political support. <p>The above elements when through three phases which Olsson et al. (2010) categorised as: (1) understanding where you are, (2) figuring out where to go, and (3) developing strategies</p>
13	The Kristianstads Vattenrike Biosphere Reserve (Olsson et al., 2010; Olsson et al., 2008)	Transforming the degraded and flooded meadows into an area of unique aesthetic, cultural–historical, and ecological values	1970 – 2000s	Recognition of the value of the flooded meadows and the threats to their future	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Designation of the areas as nature reserve and coming under the protection of Ramsar Convention Site 2. Initiation of a culture heritage program 3. Collaboration, negotiation and building trust
14	The transformation of the New Dutch Waterline (Verschuure-Stuip, 2020)	Revitalisation of military properties and turning them into heritage landscape	1980s - 2014	Changes to ownership and renewed attention to the physical remains	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Piloting 2. Linking heritation to spatial development and landscape planning 3. Adopting revitalisation on the landscape basis instead of the object level 4. Generation of new funding sources 5. Public awareness 6. Research and expertise 7. Involving a range of actors 8. Reforming of institutions (State Forestry Service) 9. Lobbying a range of actors <p>Also identified six key phases: Initiatives (1980–1993), Reflection (1993–1997), Starting (1997–2003), Transition (2003–2008), national implementation (2008–2013), and provincial implementation (2014–future)</p>
15	Melbourne water transformation (Ferguson et al., 2013)				
16	Land use Central Java & Kalimantan, Indonesia (about 8,000 people in case study)	From: Dryland rice system To: agroforestry	1994-present	Increased variability of rainfall leading to soil water deficits during rice growing season	Planned bottom-up livelihood diversification by land use change Decision making on land use change made at village scale and by local associations learning by doing: strong systems focus & local ownership

	(Colloff et al., 2020; Fedele et al., 2017)			Recognition that Agricultural production system based on dryland rice production on terraces increasingly unsustainable	
17	Coastal fishery governance, Chile (Colloff et al., 2020; Gelcich et al., 2017)	From: Commercial harvesting of Chilean abalone and collapsed fishery To: Top-down & bottom-up governance, no commercial fishing and recovered stocks	1975-1988	over-harvesting of keystone shellfish species; collapse in fisheries resource stocks	ecosystem recovery and persistence, supported by new law and fisheries governance rules co-ordinated focus on influencing political processes and decision-makers comprehensive, inclusive, integrated across scales, backed by law, based on property rights fishers empowered, governance transformed, resource stock sustainable
18	Sponge cities (integrated urban water management), China https://earth.org/sponge-cities-could-be-the-answer-to-impending-water-crisis-in-china/ (Zevenbergen et al., 2018)	From: Grey infrastructure and command and control paradigm To: Integrated urban water management with blue/green infrastructure – working with nature paradigm.	2014-present	rapid urbanisation and significant environmental and water-related problems in China's urban areas, e.g. aging/outdated water and wastewater infrastructures, urban flooding, combined sewer overflow, water quality deterioration, water scarcity, and a high frequency of extreme weather	30 pilots undertaken. Each involves a highly contextual IUWM strategy Sponge cities incorporate a range of green and grey infrastructures such as interconnected greenways and waterways, contiguous open green spaces, green roofs, porous design interventions and drainage systems, water savings and recycling initiatives. The State Council has set 2030 as the target for the sponge cities to be integrated into regional urban development plans. actively encourages PPP to help finance sponge city construction

Appendix 2: Examples of indicators (Palomo et al., 2021)

Case	Restructuring:	Path-shifting:	Multiscale:	Innovative	Systemwide:	Persistent:
Farming to empower people and conserve ecosystem services in Mexico	SOCIAL: Changing paradigms, mind-sets and Practices	SOCIAL: Increased revenues ECOLOGICAL: Reduced pressure and restoration	<i>Not identified</i>	SOCIAL: New capacities and revenue	SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL: Three regions have been involved	SOCIAL: Long-term commitment is needed
Food and water security in ejidos around the Tacaná Volcano, Mexico	SOCIAL: More interactions to exchange valuable information. ECOLOGICAL: Introduction of water-resistant varieties & protection, restoration of cloud forest and optimization of agroforestry	SOCIAL: Increased participation ECOLOGICAL: Reduced pressure. SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL: Greater food and water security and resilience	SOCIAL: Financial support from various scales and exchanging information with other regions	ECOLOGICAL: Optimization of agro-forestry systems	SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL: Whole landscape	<i>Not identified</i>

Mountain pastures and wetlands and communal management in Canchayllo, Peru	SOCIAL: Empowerment and new actors (IUCN and researchers) allowed better social organization. ECOLOGICAL: Restoration of water infrastructure	ECOLOGICAL: Increased water availability and reduced fire risk	SOCIAL: Stakeholders at various scales involved ECOLOGICAL: Upper and lower part of catchment	SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL: Combination of ancient and new technology	SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL: Whole community involved	<i>Not identified</i>
Integrated disaster risk reduction in flood-affected areas in Tajikistan	SOCIAL: Strong mobilization and collaboration in solving climate change risks ECOLOGICAL: Restoration of riverine ecosystems	SOCIAL: Higher security allows a better use of resources ECOLOGICAL: Decreased floods	SOCIAL: A foreign NGO served to start the project	SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL: Combination of grey-green infrastructure	SOCIAL-ECOLOGICAL: Whole watershed and upper and lower actors were involved.	SOCIAL: long-term sustainability through engagement

Appendix 3: Example of dimensions involved in transformative change processes (Löhr et al., 2022)

- Orientation towards multiple system elements (e.g. networks) and types (e.g. practical and political)
- Phases of (predominately) creating and maintaining and phases of (predominantly) disrupting and maintaining
- Interplay across multi-scales (local projects – national political context)

Example: Transforming to an international hub for wind power for renewable energy Hamburg, Germany

Creating	Maintaining	Disrupting
Political orientation		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating political awareness and support • Defining new rules through linking to a new national support scheme • Creating flagship projects to experiment and implement new technologies • New objectives for wind power • New targets and goals supporting land use change <u>indirectly</u> enabling wind build out 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing additional infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disrupting narrow link with land use plan by developing projects in locations not with these links (e.g. with port authority) • Coalition involving Green party replaces sole ruling party with • Defending against political opposition • Restricting use of coal
Organisation orientation		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a first wind fair • Wind fair creating a platform for innovation and networking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular wind fair with increasing numbers of actors engaging • Wind fair helping to strengthen networks and market access • Wind fair mythologised as “Woodstock of Husum” • Valorising and demonisation to maintain the wind fair in face of competition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defending the wind fair and resisting being subsumed into a less successful fair in Hamburg city to reach international and national audiences.
Networks orientation		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a local platform for the wind energy association by a local wind pioneer through a new wind group • Wind pioneer worked to create new networks around a common identity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approach of wind pioneer mythologised for support to wind sector • Regular meeting of local wind group • Focus on increasing members to sustain network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disrupting existing assumptions about the riskiness of hydrogen for energy generation

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wind group narrative created in collaboration with local politicians and experts via panel discussions • Panel discussions create opportunities for learning in the network 		
Technology orientation		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Area formally identified in land use plan as wind priority area with defined targets established. • New idea to create a research wind park to enable experimentation created in collaboration with local planner responsible for the site • Citizen initiative formed against site development • Regular checks created to monitor areas of concern 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opposition demonize plans • Supporters valorised plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local referendum held to defend against the bypassing on existing practices to develop the wind park • Lawsuit filed against planned wind park • Proposal for wind park to produce energy for local consumption to disrupt and bypass existing opposition

Appendix 4: Phase of transformation (expanding on Moore et al., 2014)

Triggers or Pre-transformation	Preparing for change	Navigating the change process	Institutionalizing
Social/ political/ecological events (often in combination) create (or are linked by actors) to create potential windows of opportunity for deliberate change. Social: civil unrest/ social movement around a shared concern (e.g. climate change) Political: election cycle/ new government/ new policy (e.g. EU Green Deal) Socio-ecological: Recognised collapse in ecosystems and natural resources/ negative consequences of natural hazards (e.g. flooding/ drought). Technological: new means of production/ technology	Individuals and collectives working to understand the current situation, how and what to change to build collective action frames that provide a common narrative and vision to organise networks, ideas, resources and activities around. Building understanding through experimentation/ learning through action approaches for innovation and testing alternatives	Ideas and innovations are selected through social learning, adapted and adopted more widely. Supported by networks and social movements and the resources and capital at their disposal. Selection is shaped by (and can shape) shared visions that helps drive the transformation process (e.g. issues of equity and vulnerability)	Change is routinised (to be seen as the new normal) and supported by redirecting resources (financial and human) and enabling policy frameworks and organisational structures. New feedbacks are established and strengthened. Cross scale interconnections strengthened to support adaptative capacity (to work with system dynamics and unanticipated future perturbations) and continued scaling up efforts.

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